

DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION: ANALYSIS OF CONCEPTS AND A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH

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Abstract: This article analyzes the issues of development of environmental competence in the conditions of modern environmental education and describes concepts and a systematic approach to it.

Key words: culture, ecology, ecological education, reproductive, alternative, retrospective, ecological competence, competence, systematic approach.

INTRODUCTION. Ecological consciousness is the level of awareness of each person in his life activities that ecosystems are his habitat. An ecologically conscious person cannot always be called ecologically cultured. Because understanding the need for ecological stability does not mean that man has implemented it in his activities. Ecological culture is knowledge about ecosystems, consciousness, perception, literacy, intellectual potential and the activity of knowing how to apply it in practice, a high indicator of activity in relation to the environment, a conscious and responsible approach.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Pedagogical aspects of the foundations of environmental education, the causes of environmental risks in the era of globalization, ways to eliminate them, scientific research aimed at developing some aspects of environmental competence in students Q. Abdurahimov, I. Kh. Ayubova, P. Berdanova, N. Bozorova, R. Kh. Djurayev, Y. Ahmadaliyev, N. Isakulova, Sh. Kamolkho'jayev, A. Malikova, M. E. Musayeva, V. Nikitin, N. O'. Nishonova, H. Norbo'tayev, T. Saparov, V. N. Sattorov, H. Togayev, E. O. It was carried out by Turdikulov, U. Turdikulov, D. Tokhliyev, A.S. Tokhtayev, A. Ergashev, Sh. Yunusova.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The concept of "ecological culture" can be defined as a high level of acquisition of theoretical and practical ecological knowledge by a person. The criteria for the formation of ecological competence, in turn, are characterized by indicators" [4], It is a developed stage and a component of a certain society and world culture. Environmentally conscious activities of people in relation to mother nature define their ecological cultures. It consists of a rational and responsible relationship between nature and man. It is necessary to define "ethical ecological awareness", "ecological responsibility",

"ecological volition", "ecological values" as the basic qualities of ecological culture.

Ecological consciousness means "a person's emotional knowledge of ecosystems, the ability to perceive, perceive, imagine, compare, and compare their objects and events, and to acquire practical skills for the protection of ecosystems based on intelligence and depth" [2]. This characteristic of a person is manifested when he enters into any contact with nature, and is explained by his ability to correctly assess the result of the process.

Environmental responsibility is manifested in a person's attitude towards ecosystems and education of responsibility towards it. Such an attitude is formed only as a result of a person's desire to realize the consequences of negative impacts on ecosystems and to eliminate such negative impacts. Also, "on the basis of the economic entity's understanding of the environmental consequences of its economic activities and its voluntary obligations and readiness to take preventive measures to prevent environmental damage a conscious attitude to the normative legal requirements of protection and voluntary elimination of the damage caused to it". Environmental responsibility includes qualities such as love for ecosystems, personal responsibility, conscientiousness, devotion to duty, and caution.

Ecological voluntariness is a concept related to the assessment and control of the behavior of a person who is a conscious member of the ecosystem and the behavior of others in the environment, personal determination, careful approach, cleanliness. is the driving force of ecologically oriented real positive activity aimed at harmonizing relations" [5].

On the basis of new ecological education, scientific study and analysis of the interrelationship of the ecological and moral environment, identifying problems and finding measures to solve them, preventing the negative effects of environmental threats on the development of society and people's quality of life, focusing on raising the environmental consciousness of the population, it is important to warn the population and, moreover, the whole humanity of future dangers. Human influence on nature is in three directions: firstly, in the process of using natural resources, influencing natural objects; secondly, in the process of protecting, conserving, restoring, and increasing natural resources; thirdly, it is manifested in ensuring the ecological safety of natural objects [6].

The moral qualities of a person formed in the ecological environment are evident in his positive attitude towards nature and lead to a serious sense of duty and responsibility towards nature and society. This becomes an important

moral factor of rational use of natural resources, its protection and environmental safety. Eco-ethical culture formed in an ecological and ethical environment, combined with the ecological legal consciousness and knowledge of each person, turns into a driving force of his creative activity. Spiritual values are important in rational management of nature-society-human relations of environmental ethics norms. The system of values is the basis of universal culture, and stable attitudes towards them form the core of culture. It is important to show the importance of values in the formation of a person's environmental ethics: a person can be a citizen of different countries, but he cannot be civilized without loving nature and preserving it. A person can be a master of his profession, but without preserving the natural environment in which he lives, grows and works, without protecting its purity and cleanliness, without complying with the requirements of environmental law, he is neither moral nor civilized. can't. The feeling of respect and love for nature is not given to everyone, forming such feelings and perfecting the basics of ecological culture is a very difficult task. Ecological culture formed in a moral environment is formed through moral norms about goodness, evil, justice, injustice, etc. in relation to the environment, natural environment. Such ideas, norms define and control the essence, motive of people's behavior. As each individual learns ethical views and rules about ecology and the environment, starting from a certain ecological environment, he turns them into his own moral virtues and beliefs, which, of course, forms the basis of ecological culture and creates a new ethical environment. causes formation. As much as universal moral norms are followed in human interactions, it becomes necessary to have such ethical attitude towards nature in a certain ecological environment.

The main goal of ecological education is to ensure the unity of ecological education, upbringing and practice in order to achieve the safety of ecosystems that ensure the sustainable development of current and future generations. In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to fulfill the following environmental tasks at the national level: development of universally recognized scientific and theoretical foundations of ecology; evaluating its history, current state and future prospects in the context of various ecosystems; development of an environmental concept and program of actions; adoption of tactical and strategic environmental development plans; revision of the personnel training system for ecology and environmental protection; comprehensive analysis of the environmental legal base and creation of a mechanism for connecting it with practice; implementation of the mandatory principle of national environmental

education; encourages solving issues such as revising environmental education in accordance with the principles of sustainable development. Also, environmental security is an integral part of national security, and it differs from other security factors in its hidden nature. That is why the policy of training qualified environmental personnel in the national education system is one of the most urgent problems of our time.

Based on a systematic approach, the mechanisms of interaction between pedagogical activities and the control environment in the development of environmental competence of students include the following processes: the main goal of developing environmental competence in students is the training of qualified personnel in higher pedagogical educational institutions in accordance with the state order and society's requirements; The state educational standards stipulate that the graduate should perform teaching, educational, teaching-methodical, production and scientific-research tasks in the pedagogical activity.

In the gradual and continuous organization of education in the field of nature protection, it is relatively common to rely on the system of family, pre-school education institutions, schools, educational institutions, labor teams. Based on the historical and logical principles of this scheme, there is no doubt that it will ensure the continuity of education. However, urgent environmental problems of today require a massive strengthening of this work at all levels. In order to increase the efficiency of nature protection work, it is of great importance to eliminate the deep-rooted indifference and "self-centeredness" mood in the minds of farm managers. After all, increasing the environmental responsibility of leaders and experts today by all means may bear fruit tomorrow. In this process, ecological education does not consist in the formation of theoretical views about nature, "at the same time, it also implies the formation of faith and practical training" [3]. After all, one of the main tasks of environmental education is to theoretically justify conflicts between nature and society in daily life activities, and to independently find practical solutions.

The concept of development of environmental education in the Republic of Uzbekistan "taking into account the fact that environmental problems are gaining global importance, in recent years, environmental protection, environmental culture, environmental education, environmental enlightenment, along with important priorities special attention is paid to the issues. The relevance of ecological education is determined by the need to protect the nature, ecosystems, environment of our country from instability and derailment, to increase the environmental culture of the population, to contribute to these

very serious and vital issues of all layers of the population, especially young people" [1]. Therefore, it follows that environmental education and training is aimed at eliminating such problems.

Another goal of environmental education is to teach the basics of theoretical knowledge about the protection of the natural environment, to familiarize with the content and essence of the current environmental policy, and serves to form the practical skills of workers in this field. It also fulfills the task of forming a person's organizational abilities, needs, interests, responsibilities, ways of thinking, in accordance with ecological principles and norms in managing a person's economy. In the process of ecological education and upbringing, the discipline of protecting natural resources, perseverance and hard work of a person are determined.

The issue of common environmental education is important in the development of ecological competence. It shows two relatively independent processes:

the possibility of a complex and systematic approach to environmental education arises from the need to harmonize different areas of education, to connect alternative directions based on a single goal.

it is necessary to preserve the historical and logical consistency of connections between different forms and levels of ecological education, and to ensure connections between their means and methods. In other words, the common character of these directions is manifested in their relationship to each other. In addition, on the basis of connecting education and training with the interests of nature protection, a commonality emerges, and its features become a necessary condition for the development of ecological responsibility.

The reform of the educational system based on environmental needs has moved universal values, including environmental education, to the center of pedagogical policy. The effective solution of this task requires the generalization of all fields of education based on scientific and philosophical methodological principles. In fact, it is in the process of environmental education that there are opportunities to eliminate the gaps and conflicts of different forms of science and social consciousness in the fields of education. Therefore, education in the field of nature protection should be an integral part of the training of qualified personnel at any level of educational complex, rather than being an event artificially and mechanistically added to general education. Its content may change depending on the social, economic, political conditions, and ecological situation in different countries.

The convergence of different levels and directions of environmental education represents the adaptation of the "individual" interests of these areas to universal interests. In this sense, it is necessary to note the educational role of other forms of activity: traditions, customs, rituals and other rituals in increasing ecological activity and responsibility. Such socio-practical events acquire a unique ecological content. That is, the complex of social values becomes a factor affecting other structural elements of society, being ecological. In particular, environmental education - with increasing responsibility in the relevant direction, remains a tool influencing the internal and external political processes of society. In the process of forming the principles of ecological activity, the culture of ecological thinking, concepts, conclusions, practical relations, socio-political beliefs, general worldview of workers are formed by mastering certain theoretical knowledge. In other words, the educational complex prepares a person for active environmental, social and political activity.

CONCLUSION. In many studies conducted in connection with the demands placed on the educational system by modern economic and social development, the competent approach was considered as a new stage of changing the content and methods of education. From this point of view, in many studies, competence is interpreted as a set of interrelated personal qualities necessary for productive and creative activity, and competence is interpreted as the acquisition of necessary competencies by a person that allows solving any problem in a certain field.

In conclusion, the development of environmental education and training in modern educational conditions, the organization of a pedagogical process aimed at forming a careful attitude to the environment affects the development of environmental knowledge and skills in students. That is why it is important to use new approaches aimed at developing environmental competence, and to use various impact mechanisms.

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